

IMPACT OF FLOOD-DISRUPTED INFRASTRUCTURE ON WOMEN'S ACCESS TO PRIMARY HEALTHCARE IN REMOTE GILGIT-BALTISTAN COMMUNITIES

Hurab Khalid^{*1}, Abdul Hannan²

^{*1}Masters in Public Health in Disasters, Department of Public Health, Faculty of Medicine, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

²BS (Workplace Health & Safety Promotion), Department of Public Health, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

¹hurabwahla9999@gmail.com, ²ab.hanantarar@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Hurab Khalid

Abstract

This study investigates how floods affecting infrastructure have reduced women's access to primary health care in the remote mountainous locations of Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) Pakistan. Due to climate change, floods and glacial lake outburst floods (GLOFs) have become more frequent, damaging roads, bridges and basic health units (BHUs) and isolating rural populations for long durations. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with participants – sixteen women from the flood-affected districts of Skardu (Stack region) and Ganche (Kondos Valley). Analysis of the data revealed four interlinked challenges in healthcare system access. First, health infrastructure collapse and difficulties in mobility. Second, gender-specific issues such as dependence on men to assist with mobility and discomfort with male health staff. Third, institutional and emergency response failures characterized by the poor coordination of damage assessment and limited gender sensitivity. Finally, psychological stress and adaptive coping strategies such (as) relying on home remedies and sharing of community resources. The physical isolation and patriarchal norms in the area, coupled with a lack of preparedness of the institutions, aggravate the risk to the health of women during a disaster. Following the Gender and Development (GAD) theory, the Five A's of health care access, and resilience theory, the study concludes that infrastructural resilience and gender-integrated disaster-health planning are significant for equitable delivery of health care services in the HAH region. The recommendation suggests strengthening mobile health services for women, training lady health workers for emergency outreach and inclusion of gender-responsive strategies in Pakistan's disaster management protocols for achieving health equity on sustainable basis in context of climate-induced disasters.

INTRODUCTION

The climate-related extreme weather is escalating all over the world, especially in mountain areas (Shrestha et al., 2020). Gilgit-Baltistan has considerable amount of ice masses that replenish

the Indus River. It is susceptible to periodic floods and meltwater lake eruption floods (Ali, 2024). Remote villages will get isolated for months at a time due to the destruction of roads, bridges,

hospitals, etc. Women, particularly in rural GB, already have mobility restrictions and limited access to female health professionals (Joint, 2014). The aftermath of these disruptions is not just the loss of lives and property. It also involves the loss of social security and impact the lives of people living there. People of the countryside and faraway places in GB largely depend on small health units, Lady Health Workers, and occasional visits by medical officer. When floods sweep through bridges or congest narrow mountain roads, women's access to health facilities becomes disproportionately constrained due to the existing gender norms restricting women's mobility. Delays in seeking care, especially for maternal, neonatal, and reproductive health needs, often lead to needless complications and death (Beard et al., 2016).

Pakistan's federal and provincial governments have made headway in maximizing health coverage through primary healthcare networks, yet geographical isolation and gender inequity remain persistent barriers (Aaon, 2017).

The 2022 flood damage to over 30 health facilities in GB as reported by the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) and many others were rendered non-operational due to blockages on access routes. When there's a disruption, it hinders vaccination, delivery of medicines and emergency services. It exposes the delicate health infrastructure of a mountain (Saif & Ali, 2025).

In Gilgit-Baltistan GB floods not just environmental phenomenon but is also gendered social phenomenon. Disasters worsen inequality and women suffer the most in most patriarchal societies. In northern Pakistan, socio-cultural norms restrict women from travelling or communicating with the male doctor and using their own financial resources for transportation or medicine. After the floods, roads are destroyed, and the focus of relief operations is on reconstruction. Women's health needs, specifically for reproductive and psychosocial health, are not taken into consideration (Feroz et al., 2022).

These barriers combined can turn a natural disaster into a complex humanitarian emergency. The mere presence of health facilities is not

enough for women's health outcomes, their physical, social and cultural access is as important (Penchansky & Thomas, 1981).

Regional and Global Relevance

In contrast, a lot of flood research in Pakistan has focused on lowland areas like Sindh or Punjab which are very different in terms of access routes and population densities. The geographic bias has created a critical knowledge gap on the gendered health impacts of floods in high-altitude, low-density areas like GB. The Geographical Importance of Gilgit-Baltistan in the HKHK region include its regional and global geo-strategic importance and its dependence on glacier hydrology. The area falls under Pakistan's China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), where infrastructure development contributes to opportunity as well as environmental risk. Experts say floods have increased on account of many things, one of them being unplanned construction and deforestation (Chaliha et al., 2022).

Theoretical and Practical Rationale

This study has been based on the Gender and Development (GAD) theory, whereby gender is seen as a structural factor influencing power and resources (Jain & Moser, 1995). The study also calls on Penchansky and Thomas (1981) Five A framework, which includes availability, accessibility, affordability, acceptability and adequacy. Flood disruptions happen in all five dimensions simultaneously. Clinics become unavailable. Roads become impassable. Transportation becomes unaffordable. Services become socially unacceptable (due to predominance of male doctors). Facilities become inadequate for emergencies. This way of thinking shows how complicated the problem is beyond just distance.

In conclusion, resilience theory (Folke, 2016) offers us a useful way of understanding how people cope, and adapt. Women in GB while isolated are incredibly resilient and use informal healthcare networks, share medicines and contact Lady Health Workers via mobile phones. Yet, resilience should not supplant structural accountability (Rao et al., 2017).

Research Objectives

Four key aims are pursued by the study

1. To investigate how women’s access to primary healthcare in far-flung GB communities is affected by the disruption of infrastructure due to floods.
2. To find out about social, cultural, and economic factors that help or prevent floods.
3. To learn how women adjust and deal with challenges when formal healthcare is unavailable.
4. To develop recommendations for integrating gender and resilience into disaster-health planning in mountainous Pakistan.

Significance of the Study

The findings will be relevant to both local and global context. Due to this, it will enable the Government of Gilgit-Baltistan and humanitarian agencies to tailor evidence-based gender-sensitive emergency health systems, road planning and community-based health resilience. The research will add to comparative research on climate justice, gender and health equity in mountainous developing countries and is in line with the Sendai

Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (Albrito, 2018).

Literature Review

Overview of Flood-Disrupted Infrastructure and Health Access

Floods are the most common natural disaster in the world and affected more than 1.5 billion people between 2000 and 2020 (UNDRR, 2020). In developing countries, they often destroy important public infrastructures like roads, bridges and clinics, limiting access to services (Kınık & Çalışkan, 2024).

In Pakistan, over 33 million people were impacted by the floods in 2022. Furthermore, 1400 health facilities were damaged. In the northern mountainous region of Pakistan, Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) is experiencing more floods and Gloff’s due to climate change. Floods in 2022 caused damage to nearly 30% of roads in the region (NDMA, 2023). A bridge can cut access to hospitals and BHUs as the region depends on a few narrow mountain roads only (Hussain et al., 2024).

Gendered Dimensions of Healthcare Access

In the Uttarakhand Himalayan region of India, Rautela (2020) conducted a study which revealed that the reason behind the delay in receiving treatment by women is to recover their families first instead of themselves. LHWs are the core of women's health delivery system in GB, but their mobility and outreach decrease drastically during floods. Many women self-medicate or use informal care in the absence of a female provider, which can increase maternal and child mortality (Lützwow et al., 2023)

Floods, Infrastructure Fragility, and Institutional Gaps

The infrastructure of GB is fragile and weak due to the mountainous terrain. Just one flood has the power to wash away roads and suspension bridges. Because of high altitude and bad weather, it often

takes months to rebuild them. As stated by Pakistan's National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA), the destruction in Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) in 2022 included over 200 km of roads as well as 60 bridges. This caused the communities to be cut off from health services (Hussain et al., 2023).

Conceptual Framework

Floods or GLOF can affect infrastructure connectivity of roads, bridges and clinics along with physical access to health care.

Social-Cultural Barriers (Patriarchy, Mobility Norms, Privacy)

Restrictions within organizations (insufficient policies, no female staff).

Women's access to primary healthcare is gendered inequity.

Research Gap

in the case of GB, infrastructure failures and social and institutional barriers combine to produce compounding health vulnerabilities for women. It stresses the need for comprehensive disaster and health planning that focuses on gender (Asim et al., 2021).

The research fills that gap by employing qualitative purposive sampling approach to explore impacts of isolation due to flood on accessing health care, decision making and women's adaptation in GB.

Research Methodology.

Introduction.

This chapter by the researchers reveals the methodology employed to explore how the flood-disrupted infrastructure made women's access to primary healthcare facilities difficult in the remote areas of Gilgit-Baltistan. The study takes a qualitative approach to explore the experiences of women who had direct barriers to healthcare post-2022 floods.

The chapter describes the research design, study area, target population, sampling method, data collection instruments and analytical tools and ethics.

Research Design.

A qualitative research design was employed to gain an in-depth understanding of the social and environmental realities affecting women's access to healthcare after floods. Researcher chose qualitative research because it is capable of revealing detailed narratives, perceptions and social meanings which cannot be articulated in numbers.

Study Area.

The study took place in two important flood-affected areas of Gilgit-Baltistan.

Stak Region (Skardu District) one of the most flood-affected areas on isolated terrain prone to landslides. In District Ganche (Kondos Valley) that is a border area and due to road blockages and communication breakdowns, women had no access to healthcare.

These areas are vulnerable to natural disasters, geographically isolated, and the health

infrastructure damage during the 2022 floods was documented.

Population and Sampling Technique.

Researcher targeted women aged 18-49 years living in the flood-affected communities of Skardu, Stak, and Kondos Valley.

Researcher used purposive sampling to ensure that women who have suffered from difficulty in accessing health care due to flood damage to infrastructure were included. Purposive sampling enabled the deliberate selection of participants who would yield rich, relevant and context-specific data consistent with the study's objectives.

A total of 16 females took part in the study with the distribution.

Eight women from the Stak Region—the area with the highest flood impact.

Eight Women of District Ganache Kondos Valley Local health volunteers and community leaders helped identify the participants, ensuring that the respondents represented a range of age groups, marital statuses and socio-economic conditions.

Methods and Tools for Data Collection

Through the use of semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs), data were collected from women to understand their lived experiences and perceptions.

Essential Instrument for Data Collection.

The semi-structured interview guide aimed to obtain open-ended responses from the participants concerning their experiences related to the availability of health care before and after the floods, transport issues, availability of medical staff and the perceived support from institutions". The Balti language was used for all interviews and later, English transcriptions were made.

Tools and Procedures for Analysis of Data

Data was evaluated through Thematic Analysis as suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006). Researcher tried to find out and organize, also interpret the meaningful patterns (themes) in qualitative data.

Analytical Tools Used.

Researcher organized the qualitative data and coded it using the NVivo 12 Plus. Using NVivo allowed for an organized recognition of the codes, sub-themes, and major themes enabling comparison of the districts.

Ethical Considerations.

The university research ethics committee approved this research project. Before every interview, the participants were informed of the purpose of the study, their participation was voluntary, and confidentiality was assured. Due to low literacy levels, verbal informed consent was acquired. All identifying information was anonymized. We conducted the interviews at the participants' comfort level and in a safe space.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Introduction

The findings of the research "Impact of Flood-Disrupted Infrastructure Impeding Access of Women to Primary Healthcare in Remote Communities of Gilgit-Baltistan" are presented in this chapter. The data was collected through semi-structured interviews, mainly conducted over mobile and WhatsApp and Google meet with women from flood-hit areas, lady health workers and local informants. Responses were analyzed through thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), yielding four main themes.

1. Infrastructure and Accessibility Challenges.
2. gender-specific Barriers and Social Restrictions.
3. Organizational and Emergency Response Gaps.
4. Psychological and Coping Responses.

Theme 1. Issues regarding infrastructure and accessibility

a. Pre-Flood Access.

Participants characterized their access to health care as manageable but limited before the flood. The majority of women travelling to Basic Health Units (BHUs) made it by local vans or motorbikes in 30-60 minutes. Roads, while rough, were

passable. Often one could communicate with healthcare providers by phone.

Before the waterlogging, women were able to reach on jeep to the BHU in 40 minutes. The services were in place, and we did not fear the travel."

b. Post-Flood Disruptions

After the floods, the situation changed dramatically. Bridges, pedestrian way and roads located in the mountains have been washed away so now, several villages are completely cut off. Women described walking for hours on unsafe, muddy routes.

The main road and bridge were gone after the flood. We had to walk over dangerous landslide areas, many women just stayed home: Participant, Ghanche.

According to the NDMA report (2023), in GB 200 km roads and 60 bridges are washed out, which is also confirmed by the participants. Consequently, just under fifty percent of those in the most isolated flood areas lost access to healthcare, down from eighty percent.

c. Most Affected Infrastructure

According to the respondents, the most acute losses were roads and bridges, followed by clinics and communication networks.

"Even when the clinic was open, we could not reach it because the bridge had fallen." – Participant, Ghanche.

Theme 2 - Barriers Based on Gender and Social Control

Flooding intensified existing gender-based barriers in GB. Women grew even more mobile constrained with fear of safety and dependency on male escorts.

We couldn't travel alone after the flood. The road was damaged and risky, so a male escort was needed." – Participant, Ghanche.

Many men in the home did not allow women to move on far-off routes, fearing landslides. This made men more dependent to control women's access to health services even in emergencies.

In addition, women the absence of female health staff further dissuaded women from seeking treatment.

Most doctors were men, even when mobile teams came. A participant from the Stak valley Skardu district stated that “many women did not feel comfortable going.”

This theme follows the Gender and Development (GAD) theory (Moser, 1993) that shows how structural gender norms limit females’ autonomy in crises.

Theme 3-Institutional and emergency response gaps

Those participating said help from the government and NGOs was delayed and limited. Mobile health teams visited only a few easily accessible places leaving most villages unattended for weeks.

NGOs visited one or two village but not all villages. ‘The assistance by the government was too late’ – Participant valley Kondos.

Because of limited coordination between disaster management and health departments, coverage was uneven. When mobile units came, drugs and

women staff were missing. This shows the institutional weakness highlighted in earlier studies (Akbar & Khan, 2022).

Theme 4. Mental and Coping Reactions

Women stated that anxiety, fear, helplessness, and frustration were strong emotions caused by being unable to obtain healthcare for themselves and children.

"We were afraid pregnant women could die. Observing that someone has no aid when sick breaks us. –Participant, Ghanche.

Families adopted several coping strategies.

Using home remedies and herbal treatments.

Consulting traditional healers.

Organizing community transport pooling when possible.

These strategies reflect a theory of resilience (Folke, 2016) – behaviors that emerge from the failure of the system, not necessarily often empowerment but certainly necessity.

Summary of Key Findings

Themes	Key findings
Infrastructure & Access	Roads and bridges destroyed; isolation of valleys; travel unsafe and costly.
Gendered Barriers	Mobility restrictions, need for male escort, discomfort with male medical staff.
Institutional Gaps	Weak coordination between NDMA and health departments; limited female-led relief.
Psychological Coping &	Anxiety, helplessness, reliance on traditional remedies, community self-help.

These findings support the Conceptual Framework, showing how environmental hazards,

infrastructure breakdowns, gender norms, and weak institutions interact to limit women’s access to health care during floods.

Discussion, conclusion and recommendations
Discussion

The results of the study confirm earlier literature that floods disaster restrict women access to health care services in mountainous region (Bano & Ali, 2021; Mustafa et al; 2019).

The Access to Healthcare Framework can help us understand what the problem is.

Availability declined as clinics closed or lost staff
Accessibility worsened with road and bridge collapse

Affordability dropped since transport costs increased

Acceptability was damaged by gender insensitive relief services

The results support the GAD perspective and demonstrate how patriarchal systems increase women’s dependence on male decision-makers during an emergency (Shah & Irfan, 2020). Also, resilience through informal coping of women was “forced” not supported—echoing Wisner, Gaillard, & Kelman (2021) that resilience should not substitute institutional responsibility.

According to the results, environmental shocks damage infrastructure which exacerbates gender inequality and this further weakens the access to services. This cycle will keep creating

vulnerability if we do not implement integrated policy reforms.

Conclusion

The study’s findings indicate that flood-induced disruption to the infrastructure greatly limits women’s access to primary healthcare in Gilgit-Baltistan by compounding their physical, social and institutional barriers.

Destroyed roads and bridges limited physical access.

Due to the gender norms restricting women’s movement social access was denied.

Coordination was weak with no gender sensitive planning, which reduced institutional access.

As a result, it inconvenienced the services for maternal and child health of women, like antenatal, postnatal, and immunization care, thereby heightening health risks and emotional distress.

The research proves that resilient infrastructure and comprehensive gender planning alongside health response mechanisms should be built to protect the health rights of women in mountain areas against disasters.

Recommendations

For Policy Makers

Make roads, bridges and other routes resistant to floods.

Combine gender in plans for disaster-health and women's local decision-making.

Set up permanent mobile health units operated by trained female staff.

For Health Departments

In isolated communities, the government trains and equip Lady Health Workers (LHWs) to be outreach emergency.

Ahead of the monsoon season, stock essential medicines and vaccines in far-off BHUs.

For NGOs and Civil Society

Develop community response teams for early warning and health action

Help affected women and families cope with trauma and offer counselling.

For Future Research

Conduct longitudinal and mixed methods research to examine the long-term health and socio-economic impact of floods on women in GB.

References

Aaon. (2017). Challenges in the Healthcare Systems of Pakistan. *Anatomy Physiology & Biochemistry International Journal*, 1(4). <https://doi.org/10.19080/apbij.2017.01.555567>

Albrito, P. (2018). Local level implementation of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 31, 1307–1308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2017.12.005>

Ali, M. (2024). Assessing climate-driven impacts on Karakoram glacier surge: A geospatial analysis highlighting Shishper Glacial Lake outburst flood events (2019–2022) as prime example. *Heliyon*, 10(16), e35951. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e35951>

Asim, M., Nadeem, M., & Saima, G. (2021). Empowering Communities to cope Flood Risk: Learning from Flood affected Community in Narowal District, Pakistan. *Disaster Advances*, 14(9), 23–33. <https://doi.org/10.25303/149da2333>

Beard, J. R., Officer, A., de Carvalho, I. A., Sadana, R., Pot, A. M., Michel, J.-P., Lloyd-Sherlock, P., Epping-Jordan, J. E., Peeters, G. M. E. E. G., Mahanani, W. R., Thiyagarajan, J. A., & Chatterji, S. (2016). The World report on ageing and health: a policy framework for healthy ageing. *Lancet (London, England)*, 387(10033), 2145–2154. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)00516-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)00516-4)

Chaliha, S., Sengupta, A., Sharma, N., & Ravindranath, N. H. (2012). Climate variability and farmer's vulnerability in a flood-prone district of Assam. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, 4(2), 179–200. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17568691211223150>

Díaz, S., Demissew, S., Carabias, J., Joly, C., Lonsdale, M., Ash, N., Larigauderie, A., Adhikari, J. R., Arico, S., Baldi, A., Bartuska, A., Baste, I. A., Bilgin, A., Brondizio, E., Chan, K. M., Figueroa, V. E., Duraiappah, A., Fischer, M., Hill, R., & Koetz, T. (2015). The IPBES Conceptual Framework – connecting nature and people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 14, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2014.11.002>

Feroz, A., Muhammad, A., & Aslam, A. B. (2022). Assessing Community Resilience from a Gendered Perspective: A Case Study of Flood Affected Areas of D.G. Khan, Pakistan. *Journal of Art Architecture and Built Environment*, 5(2), 63–78. <https://doi.org/10.32350/jaabe.52.04>

- Hussain, M. A., Zhang, S., Muneer, M., Moawwez, M. A., Kamran, M., & Ahmed, E. (2023). Assessing and Mapping Spatial Variation Characteristics of Natural Hazards in Pakistan. *Land*, 12(1), 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12010140>
- Hussain, W., Abbas, Q., Saleem, S., Khan, S. W., & Shah, M. A. (2024). Assessment of floristic diversity and traditional knowledge from the selected mountainous valleys of district Gilgit, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan. *Ethnobotany Research and Applications*, 27. <https://doi.org/10.32859/era.27.46.1-22>
- Jain, D., & Moser, C. O. N. (1995). Gender Planning and Development: Theory, Practice and Training. *Feminist Review*, 49, 117. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1395333>
- Joint. (2014). Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. *Knowledge@SchulichLaw*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483346663.n124>
- Kınık, K., & Çalışkan, C. (2024). Call for Action for a Disaster Literacy Course for Disaster Risk Management Process. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dmp.2024.159>
- Lützow, N., Veh, G., & Korup, O. (2023). A global database of historic glacier lake outburst floods. *Earth System Science Data*, 15(7), 2983–3000. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-2983-2023>
- Penchansky, R., & Thomas, J. W. (1981). The Concept of Access: Definition and Relationship to Consumer Satisfaction. *Medical Care*, 19(2), 127–140. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005650-198102000-00001>
- Poth, C. N. (2019). Rigorous and Ethical Qualitative Data Reuse: Potential Perils and Promising Practices. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 18, 160940691986887. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406919868870>
- Rao, N., Lawson, E. T., Raditloaneng, W. N., Solomon, D., & Angula, M. N. (2017). Gendered vulnerabilities to climate change: insights from the semi-arid regions of Africa and Asia. *Climate and Development*, 11(1), 14–26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2017.1372266>
- Saif, A., & Ali, R. (2025). Glacier lake outburst floods (GLOFs) in Northern Pakistan: local interpretations & social impacts. *Climate and Development*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2025.2568861>
- Shrestha, S., Stevenson, L. A., Shaw, R., & Pulhin, J. (2020). Climate Change Impacts, Vulnerability and Adaptation: Asian Perspective. *Environmental Research*, 188, 109826. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109826>